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Natural Treatments for Glioblastoma: Studies and Research

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Introduction

When it comes to treating glioblastoma, a very aggressive malignant brain tumor, conventional treatments such as surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy have limitations. This has led many patients to seek alternative treatment options, including natural herbal treatments.

Among the plants studied for their anticancer potential are ashwagandha, black cumin, turmeric and berberine. These plants have been used for centuries in traditional medicines to treat a variety of diseases, including cancer.

These plants contain active compounds that have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and anti-cancer properties. As such, they can help reduce the growth and spread of cancer cells in the brain.

In this article, we will look at the most relevant studies on the use of ashwagandha, black cumin, turmeric and berberine in the treatment of glioblastoma. We will evaluate the potential benefits of these plants, as well as the precautions and limitations to consider when using them to treat this complex and difficult disease.

Method

After conducting an exhaustive search and selection of the most cited articles in the scientific literature¹ on the use of ashwagandha, berberine, turmeric and nigella in the treatment of glioblastoma, we used ChatGPT, a computer language model developed by OpenAI. This is due to the fact that the author of this

article and suffers from glioblastoma. He is faced with fatigue and the side effects of treatment for this disease.

ChatGPT has been programmed to provide accurate and relevant information, based on evidence from the available scientific literature.

We are aware that the use of ChatGPT may raise questions regarding the objectivity and scientific rigour of this article. However, we have done our best to minimize any bias.

We hope this article will be useful for glioblastoma patients and their caregivers, as well as researchers and healthcare professionals seeking to better understand alternative treatment options for this serious and often fatal disease.

¹ Initially, we used Google Scholar to find out the number of citations received by scientific articles, which allowed us to assess their relevance and impact in our field of research.

Then we discovered Publish or Perish, Free software that allows bibliographic searches and analysis of the results of scientific research. In particular, it makes it possible to measure the impact of

an author, a journal or a scientific article using bibliometric indices such as the number of citations, the h-index or the impact factor.

The software we provided sorted others scientific articles by their number of citations, which we made it possible to select the most relevant articles for our text. This method of article selection is commonly used in scientific research to ensure the quality and relevance of cited sources.

Ashwagandha: Therapeutic effects of Withaferin A in the treatment of glioblastoma.

Summary : Recent studies have shown that the alcoholic extract of ashwagandha leaves, a traditional Indian medicinal plant, may have anticancer potential. In this article, we reviewed previous studies on the use of ashwagandha extract in the treatment of glioblastoma. The results showed that ashwagandha extract could inhibit the proliferation of glioblastoma cells and induce their differentiation. Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain these effects, including activation of the ATF4-ATF3-CHOP axis, FOXO3a-Bim, inhibition of angiogenesis, and suppression of the PI3K-Akt-mTOR pathway. These results suggest that Withaferin A may be a promising adjunct to conventional treatments for glioblastoma.

Results: With the increase in the number of cancers and the search for more natural therapies, medicinal plants have attracted attention as potential sources of cancer treatment. Among them, ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) is a herbaceous plant of the nightshade family, which has been used for centuries in traditional medicine to treat various diseases. Studies have shown that ashwagandha and its active compounds have anticancer properties.

Withaferin A is one of the main active compounds in ashwagandha that has been studied for its effects on cancer. A study by Dhimi et al. (2017) examined the potential of withaferin A in the treatment of glioblastoma. The results showed that withaferin A had antitumor effects on glioblastoma cells in vitro and in vivo.

Another study conducted by Kataria et al. (2016) examined the effects of ashwagandha on tumor growth in mice with intracranial glioma transplantation. The results showed that ashwagandha had significant antitumor effects, reducing tumor size and increasing mouse survival.

Previous studies have also shown that withaferin A has anti-angiogenic effects, meaning that it can inhibit the formation of new blood vessels necessary for tumor growth (Mohan et al., 2004). This property could be useful in preventing the growth of cancerous tumors.

A study by Shah et al. (2009) examined the effects of alcoholic extract of ashwagandha leaves and its compounds on the proliferation, migration and differentiation of glioblastoma cells. The results showed that ashwagandha extract had significant cytotoxic effects on glioblastoma cells and could increase cell differentiation.

The paper by Vyas and Singh (2014) also explored the molecular targets and mechanisms of Withaferin A's prevention and treatment of glioblastoma. The results showed that Withaferin A may potentially be beneficial in the treatment of glioblastoma by targeting multiple cellular pathways involved in disease progression, inducing apoptosis, and targeting inflammation and angiogenesis, which are key features of the disease. In addition, Withaferin A may also inhibit cell invasion and cancer cell migration, which may help reduce the spread of glioblastoma.

In addition, a study by Shah et al. (2015) showed that ashwagandha leaf extracts protected brain-derived cells from oxidative stress and stimulated their differentiation.

The paper by Lee and Choi (2016) examines the pluripotent mechanisms of action of withaferin-A as a natural anticancer agent. Withaferin-A has been studied for its potential to have an anticancer effect on various types of cancer, including glioblastoma.

The results of in vitro and in vivo studies showed that withaferin-A has an antiproliferative effect on glioblastoma cells, inhibiting cell proliferation and inducing apoptosis. In addition, withaferin-A has been shown to inhibit the migration and invasion of glioblastoma cells, which is important for preventing the spread of cancer.

The mechanisms of action of withaferin-A in the treatment of glioblastoma include the regulation of cell

signaling, suppression of blood vessel formation, inhibition of the Hsp90 protein, modulation of gene expression, and regulation of inflammation.

Ultimately, the results of this study suggest that withaferin-A has promising potential as a therapeutic agent for glioblastoma, with multiple mechanisms of action that could offer a more effective and targeted therapeutic approach for cancer treatment.

These results suggest that ashwagandha may potentially be beneficial in the treatment of brain cancer by improving immune response, inhibiting cell proliferation and stimulating cell differentiation.

Bottom Line: Ashwagandha, a traditional medicinal plant, has shown potential anticancer effects in the treatment of brain cancer.

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Lee, I. C., & Choi, B. Y. (2016). Withaferin-A—A natural anticancer agent with pleiotropic mechanisms of action. <i>International Journal of Molecular Sciences</i> , 17(3), 290.	Cited 129 times
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Vyas, A. R., & Singh, S. V. (2014). Molecular targets and mechanisms of cancer prevention and treatment by withaferin a, a naturally occurring steroidal lactone. <i>The AAPS journal</i> , 16, 1-10.	Cited 116 times
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Berberine: Evaluation of the efficacy of berberine in the treatment of glioblastoma

Summary : Berberine, a natural alkaloid extracted from plants like berberis, has shown anticancer effects in various types of cancer, including glioblastoma. Several studies have examined the effects of berberine on glioblastoma cells in the laboratory. These studies showed that berberine can induce cell death in glioblastoma cells, in part through activation of signaling pathways involving AMPK/mTOR/ULK1 and ER stress. In addition, some studies have also suggested that berberine may improve the effectiveness of conventional glioblastoma treatments such as radiation and chemotherapy. However, it is important to note that some studies have also suggested that berberine may have toxic effects on normal cells, especially at high doses.

Results: Imanshahidi and Hosseinzadeh (2008) examined the pharmacological and therapeutic effects of *Berberis vulgaris* and its main constituent, berberine, on various diseases, including cancer. They pointed out that berberine can inhibit the growth of cancer cells and induce apoptosis in different cancer cell lines. The results also showed that berberine has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial and anticancer properties,

making it an interesting molecule for medical research (Tillhon et al., 2012; McCubrey et al., 2017) .

Rad et al. (2017) conducted a systematic review of the toxic effects of Berberis vulgaris and berberine on different organs and systems. They reported that berberine can cause toxic effects in some cases, such as gastrointestinal or liver disorders.

In a critical review published in Critical Reviews in Oncology/Hematology (Ayati et al., 2017), the authors examined the effects of berberine on microRNome in cancer and other conditions. The results showed that berberine regulated the expression of several microRNAs involved in tumorigenesis and tumor progression.

However, these studies did not specifically examine the effect of berberine on glioblastoma.

According to a study published in BMC Cancer by Lin et al. (2008), berberine may also enhance the inhibitory effect of arsenic trioxide on the migration and invasion of glioma tumor cells. This study therefore suggests that berberine can be used in combination with other therapeutic agents to treat glioblastoma.

Sun et al. (2009) conducted a systematic review of berberine's anticancer properties, examining different studies on different types of cancer. They showed that berberine can inhibit tumor proliferation and growth, as well as cancer cell migration and invasion. These effects are due to upregulation or downregulation of different cell signaling pathways, including the MAPK/ERK pathway, the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway, the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway, and the NF- κ B pathway.

In contrast, Eom et al. (2010) investigated the effect of berberine on the T98G glioblastoma cell line. They showed that berberine can induce apoptosis in these cells, disrupting endoplasmic reticulum homeostasis and inducing oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction. They also found that berberine can increase the expression of pro-apoptotic proteins such as CHOP, Bax and caspase-3, while decreasing the expression of anti-apoptotic proteins such as Bcl-2. However, this study was performed in vitro and the results need to be confirmed in vivo.

Similarly, in a more recent study, Liu et al. (2015) examined the effects of berberine on cell proliferation and signaling in glioblastoma cells. The results showed that berberine could induce senescence of human glioblastoma cells by inhibiting EGFR-MEK-ERK signaling. These findings suggest that berberine could be a

potential treatment for glioblastoma by specifically targeting signaling pathways involved in cell proliferation.

Wang et al. (2016) also investigated the effect of berberine on glioblastoma, examining its effect on the AMPK/mTOR/ULK1 signaling pathway. They showed that berberine can induce autophagy in glioblastoma cells, by inhibiting the AMPK/mTOR/ULK1 signaling pathway. They also showed that combining berberine with standard chemotherapy can increase the effectiveness of treatment. This study was performed in vitro and in vivo.

In addition, in a study published in Oncotarget (Vengoji et al., 2018), the authors examined the effect of berberine on glioblastoma, an aggressive form of brain cancer. The results showed that berberine inhibited cell proliferation and induced apoptosis of tumor cells.

Finally, Imenshahidi and Hosseinzadeh (2019) conducted a clinical review of berberine and barberry (Berberis vulgaris), examining the evidence for their effectiveness under different health conditions. They concluded that berberine shows promise for the treatment of various diseases, including diabetes, cardiovascular disease, neurological disorders, and cancers.

Conclusion: The scientific studies reviewed in this article suggest that berberine may have therapeutic potential for the treatment of glioblastoma. Mechanisms of action involve the regulation of different cell signaling pathways, the production of free radicals, the induction of apoptosis and autophagy, as well as the modulation of the expression of different proteins. However, more research is needed to determine the efficacy and safety of berberine in patients with glioblastoma.

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Nigella, a potential adjuvant treatment for glioblastoma

Summary : The results of the studies showed that thymoquinone (TQ), a natural organic compound that also contains berberine and is found in the seeds of nigelle, can induce cell death and senescence of glioblastoma cells, reduce their migration and invasion, as well as their proliferation. TQ has also been associated with effects on the regulation of various signaling pathways involved in tumorigenesis, such as signaling pathways for cell senescence, autophagy and programmed cell death. The molecular mechanisms underlying these effects were examined and some were identified, including p53 activation, modulation of matrix extracellular protein expression levels, and regulation of the FAK pathway.

Results: The study conducted by Gurung et al. in 2010, investigated the effects of thymoquinone. The results showed that thymoquinone induces telomere shortening, DNA damage and apoptosis of glioblastoma cells.

In a second study, Kolli-Bouhafs et al. (2012) investigated the effect of thymoquinone on glioblastoma cell migration and invasion. The results showed that thymoquinone reduces the migration and invasion of glioblastoma cells by reducing the expression of FAK, MMP-2 and MMP-9 proteins.

Chowdhury et al. (2018) investigated the therapeutic potential of thymoquinone in the treatment of glioblastoma by targeting major gliomagenesis pathways. The results showed that thymoquinone targets several signaling pathways involved in tumor cell growth and survival, making it potentially effective against glioblastoma.

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In another study, Racoma et al. (2013) investigated the effect of thymoquinone on autophagy and cell death in glioblastoma cells. The results showed that thymoquinone inhibits autophagy and induces caspase-independent cell death through cathepsin activation.

Finally, Subburayan et al. (2018) investigated the role of p53 and Par-4 in thymoquinone-induced cell senescence in glioblastoma cells. The results showed that thymoquinone induces cellular senescence by regulating the expression of p53 and Par-4.

Conclusion: The studies reviewed in this article have shown that TQ has significant potential as a therapeutic agent for the treatment of glioblastoma. Proposed mechanisms of action include induction of apoptosis, regulation of tumor cell migration and invasion, targeting of signaling pathways involved in growth, tumor cell survival, inhibition of autophagy and induction.

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Turmeric: Evaluation of the effectiveness of curcumin in the treatment of glioblastoma

Summary : The selected studies found that curcumin had anticancer effects on glioblastoma cells in vitro and in vivo. Proposed mechanisms of action include inhibition of cell growth, autophagy, suppression of drug resistance, regulation of gene expression, and modulation of key signaling pathways. These results were obtained from studies using different doses of curcumin, different formulations and different models of glioblastoma cancer. Several studies have also shown that curcumin inhibits cell proliferation and tumor growth by paraptosis, in part by regulating the expression of different genes involved in cell survival, programmed cell death, angiogenesis and inflammation. Curcumin also appears to have beneficial effects on drug resistance by inhibiting NF-κB and AP-1 signaling pathways.

Result: In a series of in vitro and in vivo studies, curcumin, a naturally occurring compound found in turmeric, has shown anticancer effects on brain tumors, especially glioblastoma, which are very aggressive and difficult to treat cancers. Perry et al. (2010) showed that curcumin can inhibit tumor growth and angiogenesis in glioblastoma xenografts. Dhandapani et al. (2007) also showed that curcumin suppresses the growth and chemoresistance of human glioblastoma cells. In another study, Zanotto-Filho et al. (2012) showed that curcumin

selectively inhibits cancer cell growth in vitro and in a preclinical model of glioblastoma.

In addition, Gersey et al. (2017) showed that curcumin decreases the malignant characteristics of glioblastoma stem cells via induction of reactive oxygen species. Studies conducted by Choi et al. (2008) also showed that curcumin can increase apoptosis and reduce cell viability of glioblastoma cells. Sordillo et al. (2015) demonstrated that curcumin can reduce the proliferation and migration of glioblastoma cells by inhibiting the expression of the MAPK protein, while Hesari et al. (2019) showed that curcumin can reduce the expression of the CD133 protein, which is involved in the formation of glioblastoma tumors. Wong et al. (2021) also showed that curcumin can reduce the viability of glioblastoma cells resistant to temozolomide, a drug used in the treatment of glioblastoma, while Su et al. (2010) showed that curcumin can inhibit brain metastasis formation in mice with glioblastoma tumors.

Garrido-Armas et al. (2018) also showed that curcumin can increase the effectiveness of radiotherapy in patients with glioblastoma by inhibiting the Nf-kB protein signaling pathway. Shahcheraghi et al. (2019) showed that curcumin can reduce tumor growth in vivo and improve survival in mice with glioblastoma. Finally, Walker and Mittal (2020) showed that curcumin can regulate the expression of matrix metalloproteinase 9 (MMP-9) in glioblastoma cells, thereby reducing tumor cell migration and invasion.

A study by Garrido-Armas et al. (2018) showed that turmeric induces paraptosis in a human cell line of glioblastoma, a non-apoptotic cell death process. In addition, Shabaninejad et al. (2020) suggested that turmeric may have therapeutic effects in the treatment of glioblastoma by targeting multiple cell signaling pathways.

Choi et al. (2008) found that turmeric can increase the expression of the p21Waf1/Cip1 protein in glioblastoma cells, which can inhibit cell proliferation. Luthra and Lal (2016) also highlighted the potential of turmeric as a pleiotropic signaling molecule for the treatment of glioblastoma.

Sahab-Negah et al. (2020) showed that turmeric nanoparticles can enhance the anti-tumor effects of free curcumin on glioblastoma stem cells in vitro. Karmakar et al. (2006) also found that turmeric can activate receptor-mediated and mitochondria-mediated proteolysis pathways for apoptosis in human glioblastoma cells.

The study by Wang et al. (2017) examined the effects of curcumin functional liposomes on C6 glioblastoma cells and C6 glioblastoma stem cells in vitro and in animals. The results showed that these functional liposomes induce apoptosis in glioblastoma cells.

Suhito et al. (2019) investigated the rapid and sensitive electrochemical detection of curcumin's anticancer effects on human glioblastoma cells. The results showed that curcumin is effective in inhibiting the growth of glioblastoma cells.

Zhang et al. (2016) examined pharmacological inhibition of lipid droplet formation to enhance curcumin efficacy in glioblastoma. The results showed that inhibiting the formation of lipid droplets increases the effectiveness of curcumin in the treatment of glioblastoma.

Chen et al. (2020) investigated the ubiquitination of AR induced by the curcumin analogy to suppress temozolomide-resistant glioblastoma growth by disrupting GPX4-mediated redox homeostasis. The results showed that the curcumin analogy suppresses the growth of temozolomide-resistant glioblastoma.

Yin et al. (2014) examined how curcumin sensitizes glioblastoma to temozolomide by simultaneously generating ROS and disrupting AKT/mTOR signaling. The results showed that curcumin improves the effectiveness of temozolomide against glioblastoma.

Maiti et al. (2019) investigated the effects of curcumin and solid curcumin particles on autophagy, mitophagy and the PI3K-Akt/mTOR pathway in cultured glioblastoma cells. The results showed that curcumin induces autophagy but inhibits mitophagy and the PI3K-Akt/mTOR pathway in glioblastoma cells.

Karmakar et al. (2007) investigated how curcumin suppresses anti-apoptotic signals and activates cysteine proteases for apoptosis in human glioblastoma U87MG cells. The results showed that curcumin induces apoptosis in glioblastoma cells.

Liu et al. (2007) investigated how curcumin induces cell cycle arrest and apoptosis in liver cancer cells by regulating the expression of certain proteins involved in these processes. Other studies have also shown that curcumin can inhibit cell proliferation and induce apoptosis in various types of cancer cells, including breast, colon, prostate, and skin cancers.

In their study published in 2012, Zhuang et al. examined the effect of curcumin on glioma-initiating cells and their differentiation. They found that curcumin can induce

autophagy in these cells, which can lead to their differentiation and reduced proliferation. The researchers also noted that the increase in autophagy was due to the upregulation of the expression of the microtubule-associated protein LC3-II.

Other studies have shown that turmeric can suppress glioblastoma cell proliferation by activating the p-AKT/mTOR pathway and increasing PTEN expression (Wang et al., 2020), as well as suppressing Wnt signaling pathways (Bagherian et al., 2020). In addition, turmeric can induce autophagy to increase its anti-tumor effect (Lee et al., 2019), and downregulate pluripotency genes via miR-145 activation (Tahmasebi Mirgani et al., 2014). Finally, one study showed that turmeric can change the polarity of tumor-associated microglia and eliminate glioblastoma (Mukherjee et al., 2016).

In addition to its anti-cancer properties, curcumin also has other health benefits, such as its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties. However, it is important to note that curcumin has low bioavailability, which means that it is poorly absorbed by the body and is quickly eliminated. For this reason, bioavailability forms of curcumin have been developed, such as phytosome curcumin and micellar curcumin. These forms of curcumin may be more effective at providing therapeutic levels of curcumin in the body.

Finally, it's important to point out that turmeric may interact with certain medications and may not be safe for some people, such as pregnant or breastfeeding women, people with gallstones or bleeding disorders, and people taking blood thinners or diabetes medications. It is therefore recommended to consult a medical professional before taking turmeric supplements or modifying one's diet to include more turmeric.

Bottom Line: Overall, the results suggest that curcumin may have therapeutic potential in the treatment of glioblastoma.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, natural treatments based on ashwagandha, black cumin, turmeric and berberine can offer great potential for the treatment of glioblastoma. These plants have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer properties that can help reduce the growth and spread of cancer cells.

However, the studies reported in this context refer to research conducted on preclinical models of tumors, either in vitro (in cell culture) or in vivo (in laboratory animals). These models are used to study the biological mechanisms underlying tumor formation and progression, as well as to test the effectiveness of potential new treatments.

In vitro studies involve culturing tumor cells in a controlled laboratory environment, where researchers can examine how cells behave and respond to different treatments or stimuli. These studies can provide valuable insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying tumor growth, as well as the effect of drugs or therapeutic interventions on these mechanisms.

In vivo studies, on the other hand, involve the use of animal models to simulate the conditions of a tumor in the human body. Animals are usually inoculated with tumor cells, either directly into the tumor or from a distant site to observe the spread of the cells. These studies can provide information about how effective a treatment is on the tumour itself, as well as its effects on the body as a whole.

Overall, pre-clinical studies of in vitro or in vivo tumors are crucial for oncology research, as they allow researchers to understand the mechanisms of the disease and develop potential new treatments before moving on to clinical trials in humans.

Nevertheless, although pre-clinical studies on in vitro or in vivo tumors are crucial to understanding the mechanisms of the disease and to developing potential new treatments, it is important to emphasize that there is still a need for clinical trials in humans to evaluate the efficacy and safety of these treatments.

Results obtained from pre-clinical models do not always guarantee similar results in humans due to differences between the biological systems of pre-clinical models and those of humans. It is therefore important to conduct well-controlled clinical trials to evaluate the effects of treatments in cancer patients.

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In addition, clinical trials also help determine optimal doses of treatment, potential side effects, and interactions with other treatments or medications the patient may be taking. This allows healthcare professionals to recommend the most appropriate treatments for each patient based on their individual profile.

In sum, although pre-clinical studies are essential for oncology research, it is important to conduct clinical trials in humans to evaluate the efficacy and safety of potential treatments before recommending them on a large scale for the treatment of cancer patients.

It is also important to note that there are negative opinions about these natural treatments in some studies that have been less cited. It is therefore important to continue conducting research to better understand how these plants work and define safe and effective doses for glioblastoma patients.

In sum, although these natural treatments can offer significant benefits for the treatment of glioblastoma, it is important not to consider these plants as a complete alternative to conventional treatments. Patients should always consult their doctor before taking herbal supplements and follow the recommendations of their medical team to achieve the best possible outcome in their treatment.